

EFFECTS OF PULMONARY REHABILITATION PROTOCOL ON THE VARIABLES OF EXERCISE TOLERANCE IN A WOMAN WITH CHRONIC OBSTRUCTIVE PULMONARY DISEASE: A CASE REPORTJade Christine Alves Roque da Silva¹

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Eloisa M. G. Regueiro³Sueli A. Alves¹Edson D. Verri^{2,3}Gabriel P. Silva^{1,2}Oswaldo S. Taube^{1,2}Simone C. H. Regalo²Saulo C. V. Fabrin^{*,1,2}¹ University Center UNIFAFIBE, Bebedouro, São Paulo, Brazil.² Faculty of Dentistry of Ribeirão Preto - FORP/USP, Ribeirão Preto, São Paulo Brazil.³ Claretiano University Center, Batatais, São Paulo, Brazil.saulo.fabrin@gmail.com**ABSTRACT**

This study aimed to evaluate the effects of a pulmonary rehabilitation protocol on the variables of exercise tolerance in women with chronic obstructive pulmonary disease. A 60-year-old woman patient, BMI of 32.90 kg/m², participated in 24 sessions of a pre- and post-pulmonary rehabilitation protocol. This program consisted of four phases: stretching, aerobic exercises, resistance exercise training and relaxation. The results obtained in the six-minute walking test after the rehabilitation program showed improvement in the distance covered (Pre = 234 meters; Post = 324 meters), increase of load exercise for the UL based on the *diagonal Kabat* method (Pre = 1; Post = 3.5 kg) and increase of respiratory muscle strength. It can be concluded that the pulmonary rehabilitation protocol has provided an increase in variables of exercise tolerance in the COPD patient.

Keywords:

COPD, morbidity and mortality, cardio respiratory fitness, muscular strength, walking test.

INTRODUCTION

The main cause of chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD) is mainly the *inhalation* of tobacco *smoke* [1]. Individuals present symptoms such as dyspnea, cough, wheezing, expectoration and respiratory infections, which not only affect the lungs, but also the cardiovascular and musculoskeletal systems [2].

The damage to these systems impairs the basic daily tasks of the individual, who needs to remain seated most of the time. This excessive inactivity occurs due to dyspnea and early muscle fatigue, making more difficult any physical activity [3].

The evolution of the disease may limit the performance of activities of daily living (ADL), which are defined as occupational performance tasks that the individual performs daily as dressing, eating, bathing, as well as mobility tasks, such as turning in bed, sitting, moving or transferring from one place to another [4].

The limitations in daily life activities are common especially during COPD exacerbations. They have been associated with decline in health status, substantial mortality, reduced quality of life, reduced lung function and frequent hospital admissions [5].

Knowing the difficulties experienced by patients that involve some forms of psychological stress (fear, worries), need for motivational support and physical conditions are important factors that facilitate an early start and evolution of pulmonary rehabilitation [6].

Pulmonary rehabilitation is an evidence-based, multidisciplinary and comprehensive intervention for patients with chronic lung disorders. It is aimed to optimize functional state, increase participation and

autonomy in clinical, mental, emotional and social aspects, promoting maximum functional independence [7]. Pulmonary rehabilitation in COPD provides a number of positive factors, such as the reduction of symptoms, improvement in quality of life and increase tolerance to perform physical activity, enabling the inclusion of the individual in society [8].

One of the low-cost tests to evaluate exercise tolerance, cardio respiratory changes and functional exercise capacity of the individual is the six-minute walk test (6MWT). It is a safe, simple and easy to apply sub-maximum exercise test, the purpose of which is to evaluate functional exercise capacity and tolerance to physical exertion, with high reproducibility [9]. There is no need to use advanced equipment, and any health care professional can apply it, observing some safety measures, time, location and type of verbal encouragement [10].

With regards to physical aspects and exercise tolerance, the activity of the respiratory muscles can be accessed using measures of muscle strength. This procedure allows the diagnosis of secondary respiratory and muscular failure and provides short-and long-term data on respiratory mechanics [9]. The manovacuometer is a simple, quick and non-invasive test which measures the maximal respiratory pressures. It is used to determine the severity and consequences of pulmonary dysfunction [11].

Given the commitment and seriousness of pulmonary dysfunction, it is important to establish a pulmonary rehabilitation program for guidance and promotion of health, and therefore, improve activities of daily living [12].

This study aimed to evaluate the effects of a pulmonary rehabilitation protocol on the variables of exercise tolerance in women with chronic obstructive pulmonary disease.

METHODS

The present study was characterized as a case report. The assessment of the functional capacity and the respiratory muscle strength of a 60-year-old woman (height of 1.56 m, weight of 81 kg, and BMI of 32.90kg/m²) with a clinical diagnosis of moderate *COPD stage II* was conducted at the **Clínica Escola de Fisioterapia do UNIFAFIBE**, São Paulo, Brazil. Assistance was provided by physiotherapy students of the institution.

The patient signed a written informed consent previously approved by the local Research Ethics Committee (under N. 2.103.670), according to the Brazilian *National Health Council* (resolution N. 466/12). The participant was duly informed about the rights and obligations, risks and benefits of the procedures and was free to leave the study at any time, without any consequences concerning present or future activities.

Data collection instruments

The physical examination included height and body mass (BM), which were measured (Welmy 110FF, São Paulo, SP, Brazil) with the subject in a standing position, looking forward and barefoot. Commonly accepted BMI ranges were used: BMI < 20 kg/m², underweight; BMI 20 to 24.9 kg/m², normal weight; BMI 25 to 29.9 K/m², overweight; BMI ≥ 30 kg/m², obesity [13].

The *clinical evaluation was comprised of anamnesis, anthropometric* measures, load test for muscle strength in the upper limbs, respiratory muscle strength and six-minute walk test data. All pre- and post-exercise testing and experimental procedures were performed by the same physical therapist, at the same time of day, following the same protocol. Anamnesis and the respiratory muscle strength data were collected on the same day; the other measures were obtained on alternate days in order to avoid fatigue and dyspnea, which are common symptoms in COPD patients.

Following the physical examination, the 6MWT was performed in a 30-m corridor, 1.5 m wide in accordance with the recommendations of the *American Thoracic Society* [9]. The patient was instructed to walk as fast as he could for six minutes, with no monitoring or talking during the test, except to report any symptoms or difficulties while performing the test. Every minute, the individual was verbally encouraged to keep walking with phrases such as: "you're doing really well!", "... minutes to complete the test." The *peripheral capillary oxygen saturation* (SpO₂), heart rate (HR), symptoms of dyspnea and respiratory rate were determined by the Borg modified scale CR10. All measures and blood pressure (BP) were measured before and immediately after testing. Supplemental oxygen was not necessary during training. Two tests were conducted on the same day, with 30-minute interval between the series. The *longest distance covered* (DC) in the 30-m walkway *distance* was considered for analysis.

Respiratory muscle strength was assessed by measuring P_Imax and P_Emax, according to the procedure used by *Black & Hyatt* (1969) [14]. Both pressure levels were measured with a manometer graduated in cmH₂O and equipped with a mouthpiece (Ger-Ar[®], São Paulo, Brazil).

The maneuver was performed with the patient in a sitting position, with a nose clip. P_Imax was measured at the mouth after complete *exhalation* to *residual volume (RV)* followed by a single sustained *maximal inspiratory effort* from that lung volume against an occluded airway. For the P_Emax measurement, the patient inhaled up to the *total lung capacity*. Both pressures were sustained for at least one second. Three maneuvers were conducted with 1-minute interval between the measurements. After data collection, the greatest value (cmH₂O) obtained for P_Imax and P_Emax was selected for analysis.

To determine the initial exercise loads for RE, the subject was tested for maximal strength performing a one-repetition maximum (1RM) test for upper limbs. The exercise consisted of lifting a weight with the dominant arm and performing the second diagonal of the proprioceptive neuromuscular facilitation technique. This diagonal movement was followed by flexion, abduction, and external rotation of the arm with shoulder at 90°. Initial resistance was 0.5 kg with 0.5 kg being added *each* minute until exhaustion. The exercise test could be interrupted by the observer if the patient developed compensatory thoracic movements to accomplish the exercise or if the complete amplitude of shoulder movement was not being reached [15].

Pulmonary rehabilitation protocol

Pulmonary rehabilitation Protocol (PRP) was carried out for three months, twice a week, on alternate days, totaling 24 sessions (*1 hour 40 minutes each*). After this period, the patient was re-evaluated using the same initial tests. At the beginning and at the end of the sessions, BP, SpO₂ and HR were measured for monitoring purposes. The PRP was divided into the following four steps:

Step 1: Stretching- cervical stretching (flexors, extensors, inclinators and rotators); upper limb stretching (hip flexors, extensors, adductors and abductors); and lower limb stretching (hip flexors, extensors, adductors and abductors) for 15 minutes focusing mainly on the upper limbs.

Step 2: Aerobic physical training– the cardiorespiratory workout was performed on a stationary bike. It started with 60% of maximum heart rate (HR_{max}) measured by the 6MWT, with weekly adjustment of the training load, reaching up to 85% HR_{max} during rehabilitation [16]. Supplemental oxygen was not necessary during training. The rates of perceived dyspnea sensation were monitored using the CR10BORG scale [17]. In the course of the study, the initial time for the bike workout was 30 minutes in the first 5 sessions and was later increased to 40 minutes in the remaining sessions.

Step 3: Resistance training (RT) – focused on the upper limb muscles with the patient performing the exercise based on the Kabat diagonal method with 50% of 1RM. Every 10 sessions, there was a re-assessment to adjust the load, which was later increased up to the end of the protocol. Three sets of 12 repetitions were performed with a two-minute interval between the series.

RESULTS

Following the re-assessment of the 6MWT, the heart rate, respiratory rate, blood pressure, SpO₂, as well as perception of dyspnea and lower limb fatigue according to the BORG CR10 scale at rest, and distance covered were measured prior to and after the test. The results obtained pre- and post-rehabilitation protocol showed that the distance covered by the patient increased, improving her functional capacity, as shown in Table

1.

Table 1-Comparison of 6MWT at rest pre- and post- rehabilitation

6MWT	Pre-Rehabilitation	Post-Rehabilitation
HR	80 bpm	78 bpm
RR	15 bpm	13 rpm
BP	110X60 mmHg	130X60 mmHg
SPO₂	97%	97%
BORG	0	0
DC	234meters	324meters

Heart rate (FC), respiratory rate (RR), blood pressure (BP), peripheral oxygen saturation (SpO₂), Borg scale (BORG), distance covered in meters (DC).

After re-assessment and following the protocol for the 1RM test, in which the patient has lifted weight in the primitive diagonally pattern, an improvement was observed as the initial load was 1 kg and increased to 3.5 kg. HR, perception of dyspnea, BP and SpO₂ measures were monitored at rest and immediately after the test.

Comparing the values obtained pre- and post-rehabilitation for the respiratory muscle strength, it was possible to observe the values expressed by maximal inspiratory pressure (MIP) and maximal expiratory pressure (MEP) via *manovacuometry*, as shown in Table 2.

Table 2 – Comparison of respiratory muscle strength pre- and post rehabilitation via manovacuometry

Manovacuometry	Pre-Rehabilitation	Post-Rehabilitation
PI_{max}	-66 cmH ₂ O	-75 cmH ₂ O
PE_{max}	+84 cmH ₂ O	+105 cmH ₂ O

Maximal inspiratory pressure (PI_{max}) and maximal expiratory pressure (PE_{max}), expressed in cmH₂O.

DISCUSSION

The assessment with the 6MWT showed improvement in exercise capacity when the distance covered increased from 234m before PPR to 324m after PPR. This finding corroborates that described by Tomioka et al., 2016, in a study that included 49 with COPD who attended a pulmonary rehabilitation program [18]. The PRP consisted of ground – based walking, cycling on an ergometer, and muscle training exercises for the upper and lower limbs, followed by relaxation. There was an increase in distance covered in the 6MWT pre- and post-pulmonary rehabilitation from 223.6 meters to 253.9 meters, respectively.

According to Hernandez et al., 2011, a PRP carried out from 2005 to 2009 showed an increase in the distance covered in the 6MWT (391 meters to 418meters) [19]. Rejbi et al., 2010, evaluated both patients with COPD and healthy subjects during a 3-month PRP, three times a week, using a bicycle ergometer and training exercises for the upper limb muscles [20]. The results showed that the distance covered in the 6MWT increased significantly after the rehabilitation program in healthy (600 to 789 meters) and COPD patients (504 to 620 meters).

With regards to the upper limb muscle strength, the comparison of pre- and post- rehabilitation showed improvement as the training load has increased progressively up to 3.5kg. According to Fabrin et al., 2017, conducted a case report in which a rehabilitation program included resistance training and load measured by the one repetition maximum test (1RM) for the following muscles: biceps, deltoid, latissimus dorsi, great dorsal, rhomboids, and pectoralis [21]. The results of the study indicated that the upper limb muscle strength increased after a 5-month training program, with 30% gain. Zanchet et al. (2005) evaluated the efficacy of a 6-week pulmonary rehabilitation program aimed to strengthen the upper limb muscles and observed a maximum load achieved in the test (pre-PR = 1.9 vs. post-PR = 2.6) [22].

Compared with pre-rehabilitation, the respiratory muscle strength showed improvement of P_{Imax} (66 to 75cmH₂O) and P_{E_{max}} (84 to 105cmH₂O). However, it is worth mentioning that, in the present study, no specific intervention was used to strengthen this muscle.

These results corroborate those found by Morano et al. 2013, who applied a 1-month pulmonary rehabilitation program in patients with lung cancer resection, five times a week. It was based on *incremental resistance exercise* protocol in which the upper limb performed diagonal movement (primitive diagonal) for 15 minutes [23]. Following the PRP, an improvement of the respiratory muscle strength was observed: P_{Imax} (90cmH₂O vs 117cmH₂O), respectively; and P_{E_{max}} (79 cmH₂O vs 92.9cmH₂O), respectively.

CONCLUSION

Based on the results obtained, it can be concluded that the PRP has provided an increase in variables of exercise tolerance (distance covered in the 6MWT, upper limb muscles load, and respiratory muscle strength) in a female patient with COPD. Therefore, there was improvement in the functional capacity and a clinically significant increase in patient's quality of life, also in exercise tolerance and a decrease in the risk of death.

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